

FAST FOOD PRODUCTION AS A MEANS OF SELF RELIANCE IN ONDO TOWN

BY

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A Paper Presented at the Second International Conference of Home Economics Research Association of Ghana, University of Education, Winneba, Ghana, 4th – 7th February 2009

ABSTRACT

The study examined how fast food production is used as a means of livelihood in Ondo town. Interview schedule and open-ended questionnaires were administered on sixty fast food operators selected through purposive and random sampling techniques. The major areas involved were the main market, Yaba, Idi-ishin, Sabo, Akure and Ife motor parks of Ondo town. Some of the fast foods produced were puff-puff, fish pie, chin chin, egg roll, meat pie, buns, doughnuts, sausage rolls, pop corn, fried yam and cake. Data collected were analysed using simple frequency counts and percentages. Results showed that 21.7% of the respondents went into fast food production because they could not get a government job after their education and 33.3%, because there is profit in the business. 50.1% of the respondents make an average daily profit of N20 to N500. Some of the recommendations made to combat the major challenges of the business (inadequate finance and high market prices) were the extension of micro credit scheme by the government to fast food operators and subsidized cost of raw materials. There is also the need for training in order to ensure necessary competence and skill for the business

INTRODUCTION

Fast food is the term given to food that can be prepared and served very quickly while any meal with low preparation time can be considered to be fast food. Typically, the term refers to food sold in a restaurant or store with low quality preparation and served to the customer in a packed form for take-out/take-away. Fast foods [fried fish and chips, sausage

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rolls, boiled egg, meat pie, doughnuts, egg roll, chin-chin, cake, etc] are not new. They have been in vogue especially in French countries. They are mainly prepared from convenience foods like guinea corn, wheat flour, bean flour, etc. The term "Fast Food" was recognised in a dictionary by Marriam-Webster in 1951 (Wikipedia, 2009).

Fast food outlets are take-away or take out providers, often with a "drive-through" service which allows customers to order and pick up food from their cars. Outlets may be stands or kiosks, which may provide no shelter or seating, or fast food restaurants (also known as quick service restaurants) with seating area in which customers can eat the food on the premises (Wikipedia, 2009).

Nearly from its inception, fast food has been designed to be eaten "on the go" and often does not require traditional cutlery, and is eaten as a finger food. Common menu items at fast food outlets include fish and chips, sandwiches, pitas, hamburgers, fried chicken, French fries, chicken nuggets, tacos pizza, hot dogs, and ice cream, although many fast food restaurants offer "slower" foods like chili, mashed potatoes, and salads. Fast food outlet is becoming more popular in Nigeria, examples of popular food outlets are Chicken Republic, Mr Biggs, Munchies, Tantalizers, Sweet Sensation, etc [Chy, 2006]. Many petrol/gas stations have convenience stores which sell pre-packed sandwiches, doughnuts, and hot food. Many gas stations in the United State also sell frozen foods and have microwaves on the premises in which to prepare them.

Traditional street food is available around the world, usually from small operators and independent vendors operating from a cart, table or portable grill. Common examples include Vietnamese noodle vendors, Middle Eastern falafel stands and New York City hot dog carts. Turo-turo vendors are a feature of Philippine life. Commonly, street vendors provide a colourful and varying range of options designed to quickly captivate passers-by and attract as much attention as possible (Wikipedia, 2009).

Depending on the locale, multiple street vendors may specialize in specific types of food characteristic of a given cultural or ethnic tradition. In some cultures, it is typical for street vendors to call out prices, sing or chant, play music, or engage in other forms of "street theatrics" in order to engage prospective customers. In some cases, this can garner more attention than the food itself. Some vendors represent another form of tourist attraction (Wikipedia, 2009).

The precise origins of fast food are vague, probably predating written history. Hungry people are as old as civilization itself, as are entrepreneurs eager to satisfy the hungry. Food vendors in ancient cities sold prepared items to passersby on the street. The actual foods varied greatly, depending on period and culture, but they generally comprised simple

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inexpensive food sold to people of modest means (Hogan, 1997). Fast foods served in Nigerian restaurants are expensive because of the added cost that it takes to operate these places e.g. the 24/7 generator, the armed security guard and other bills which are paid from proceeds of such hotels and food restaurants.

As a rule, immigrant groups preferred their indigenous grains: corn from the Americas, rice from Asia, and wheat from Europe. Often these served as the basis for the "peasant" foods of their homelands. On the average, one-fifth of the population of USA (45 million people) eat in fast restaurants each day. Although it is possible to eat nutritious fast foods, menus tend to be stacked with items high on most dieticians' "Avoid" list (Hogan, 1997).

Fast foods include salty French fries, beefburger, fried chicken, and pizzas with a thick cheese covering. These appeal to the Western palate by being fatty, low in fibre and nutrients but high in salt (one beffburger can contain more than 1000 miligrams of sodium). To make matters worse, they are often served with sugar-laden soft drinks or creamy milkshakes full of empty calories or fat. Those who regularly eat fast foods should be particularly selective, moderating the intake of unhealthy options and choosing healthy options, such as salads with low-fat dressings, wholegrain buns, and skimmed milk (Hogan, 1997).

Despite the widespread popularity of fast food in modern American culture, critics abound. Since the 1930s, articles and books have condemned the industry, exposing allegedly poor sanitary conditions, unhealthy food products, related environmental problems and unfair working conditions. Whether it warrants attention or not, the fast-food industry is still regularly cited for exploiting young workers, polluting and contributing to obesity and other serious health problems among American consumers.

Increased litter is another problem that critics have blamed on the fast-food industry. Selling their products in paper wrappings and paper bags, early outlets created a source of litter that had not previously existed. Wrappers strewn about city streets, especially those close to fast-food restaurants, brought harsh criticism, and often inspired new local ordinances to address the problem.

Labour activities have criticized fast-food chains' tendency to employ inexpensive teenage workers, usually offering the lowest possible wages with no health or retirement benefits. These restaurants often find it difficult hiring adults for stressful, fast paced jobs. Many critics claim that the industry preys on teenagers, who will work for less pay and are less likely to organise (Hogan, 1997).

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Self-reliance is the social and economic ability of an individual, a household or a community to meet essential needs including protection, food, water, shelter, personal safety, health and education in a sustainable manner and with dignity (Olusanya et al, 2000). Self reliance also means ability to do or decide things by yourself rather than depending on other people for help. It provides the basis for durable solutions, a foundation working towards the millennium development goals. Fast food production as a means of self-reliance will help to reduce poverty and unemployment rate.

STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

Poverty and unemployment are rapidly on the increase in Nigeria today. Many graduates of today depend on government for provision of jobs. Sometimes they have to wait for a long time before they get such government jobs. Sometimes they end up not getting government jobs.

PURPOSE/SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this study was to find out the use of fast food products as a means of self-reliance in Ondo Town.

Specifically the study was to:

- (i) find out various reasons why operators venture into the business and the food commonly produced
- (ii) find out how long operators have been in the business
- (iii) determine the average daily profit of operators
- (iv) find out whether fast food operators are skilled
- (v) identify the problems and challenges facing fast food production
- (vi) suggest ways of improving fast food production

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- (i) Why do operators venture into fast food production and what are the foods commonly produced?
- (ii) How long have operators been in the business?
- (iii) What is the average daily profit of operators?
- (iv) Are fast food operators skilled?
- (v) What are the problems and challenges of fast food production in Ondo town?
- (vi) What are the ways of improving fast food production in Ondo town?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will be of benefit to job seekers as it will enlighten them on the existence of fast foods as a means of livelihood. It will expose fast food operators and would-be operators to the importance of skill acquisition for higher efficiency.

METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

This study made use of descriptive research design. The research was carried out in the following areas of Ondo town-Main market, Yaba, Idi-ishin, Sabo, Ife and Akure motor parks.

Population

The population for the study comprised all street vendors who are engaged in fast food business in Ondo town.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sixty fast food hawkers were involved in the study altogether. Six major areas in the town were purposely selected out of which ten respondents each were randomly selected. The areas selected are believed to be the peak of activities in the town.

Instrumentation and Validation

The research instruments used in carrying out this study were open-ended questionnaires and interview schedules. The questionnaire was face validated by three experts in Food and Nutrition.

Administration of Questionnaire and Data Analysis

The questionnaires were administered by the researchers while a research assistant helped to conduct interview of non-literate respondents. Data collected were analysed with the aid of frequency counts and simple percentages.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The findings of the study have been presented in the following tables:

Table 1 shows that almost all (95%) those who engaged in the business are between 10 to 40 years i.e. youths. Majority of the respondents (76.7%) are female while 23.3% are male. There are more married women (51.7%) than single ones (45%) in the business. 43.3% had secondary education, 28.3% primary education and 20% had tertiary education.

Table

Class

Age

10-20

21-30

31-40

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Table 1: Socio-Economic Background of Respondents

Classification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
10-20	19	31.7
21-30	20	33.5
31-40	18	29.8
41-50	3	5.0
Total	60	100%
Sex		
Male	14	23.3
Female	46	76.7
Total	60	100%
Marital Status		
Married	31	51.7
Single	27	45
No Response	2	3.3
Total	60	100%
Academic Qualification		
Primary Education	26	43.3
Secondary Education	17	28.3
Tertiary Education	12	20
No formal Education	4	6.7
No Response	1	1.7
Total	60	100%

Research Question 1

Why do operators venture into fast food production and what are the foods commonly produced?

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Reasons for Going into Fast Food Production

Reason(s)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
I was unemployed after my education	13	21.7
It is profitable	20	33.3
It is my hobby	15	25
It is a part time business	6	10
No response	6	10
Total	60	100

Thirty three percent of the respondents believed there was money in the sale of fast food; 21.7% went into the business because they were unemployed after their education, 25% said it was their hobby; 10% as part time business. It can therefore be concluded that respondents went into the business because first they felt they could succeed in the business; secondly because they did not get job after leaving the school and thirdly as a hobby and a part time job. Fast foods commonly produced are puff-puff, fish pie, fried yam, pop-corn, chin – chin, meat pie, doughnuts, cake, egg rolls, buns and sausage rolls.

Research Question 2

How long have operators been in the business?

Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Years of Respondents in the Business

Years in business	Frequency	Percentage
1	3	5.0
2	16	26.7
3 – 5	25	41.7
6 – 10	7	11.7
11 – 22	2	3.3
No response	7	11.6
Total	60	100

Five percent of the respondents have been in the business for one year; approximately twenty-seven percent for two years; forty two percent have been in the business for 3 – 5 years. Approximately 12% have been in the business for 6 – 10 years while 3% have been in the business for 11 – 22 years.

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Research Question 3

What is the average daily profit of operators?

Table 4: Percentage Distribution of Average Daily Profit of Operators

Average Daily Profit	Frequency	Percentage (%)
₦20 – ₦500	30	50.1
₦501 – ₦1,000	17	28.4
₦1001 – ₦1,500	3	5.0
₦1,501 – ₦2,000	3	5.0
₦2,100 – ₦6,000	3	5.1
No response	4	6.4
Total	60	100

Most of the respondents (50.1%) had an average daily profit of ₦20 to ₦500, 28.4% make ₦501 to ₦1000. The highest average daily profit is ₦20 to ₦500. This confirms that there is money in the business.

Research Question 4

Are fast food operators skilled?

Table 5: Responses on Skill Acquisition of Respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Formal training	13	21.7
Informal training	29	48.3
No training	18	30
Total	60	100

A little over forty-eight percent (48.3%) of the respondents did not go to school to learn the skill of fast food production. 21.7% went to school. We can conclude that most of the respondents are not trained for the work.

Research Question 5

What are the problems and challenges of fast food production in Ondo town?

Table 6: Problems and Challenges of Fast Food Business in Ondo town

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Inadequate finance	14	23.3
Insufficient patronage by customers	4	6.7
High cost of ingredients in the market	24	40
The economic condition of the country	9	15
Sales on credit	3	5
Epileptic power supply	1	1.7
Insufficient manpower	3	5
No response	2	3.3
Total	60	100

Forty percent of the respondents are faced with the problem of high cost of materials in the market. 23.3% with inadequate finance and 15% with problems emanating from the economic condition of the country.

Research Question 6

What are the ways of improving fast food production in Ondo Town?

Table 7: Suggestions on Improvement of Fast Food Production in Ondo Town

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Availability of loan to finance the business	18	30
Improvement on the nutrient quality and safety of products	2	3.3
Reduced cost of raw materials	16	26.7
Increased patronage by customers	13	21.7
Eradication of credit sales	1	1.7
Additional production facilities	8	13.3
No response	2	3.3
Total	60	100

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The highest percentage of respondents suggested availability of loan from government, banks and individuals to be able to improve on fast food production. 21.7% suggested that if more people can patronize them there will be improvement. 26.7% suggested that government should reduce the cost of raw materials for them to improve on their production.

DISCUSSION

The study discovered that majority of those engaged in the business are the youths (between 10 and 40 years). This corresponds to Hogan's opinion (1997) that the fast food industry is cited for exploiting young workers. Today, approximately two million workers are employed in the areas of food preparation and food serving including fast food in the USA (Wikipedia, 2009). 43 % of the respondents did not go to school to learn the skill of fast food production. Wikipedia (2009) suggested that proper training is crucial for the orderly and quick service customers expect. Policies and procedures (method of preparation, hygiene practices, etc) need to be explained to would-be job seekers. They also need to be taught to acquire the needed skills.

It was also discovered that the highest number of respondents (50.1%) make an average daily profit of N20 to N500.00. This confirms that there is money in the business, Wikipedia (2009) also supported this with reference to the forecast of the National Restaurants Association that fast food restaurants in the U.S. would reach US \$142 billion in sales in 2006 (a 5% increase over 2005).

CONCLUSION

Fast food production can be relied upon as a means of livelihood and self-reliance. If the government and banks can give loans to help those who want to go into this business to set up, expand and produce good and qualitative fast foods, production will be encouraged on a small scale and at prices within the reach of the masses. Government and skilled individuals can set up skill acquisition and training centres for operators and would be operators.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are made to enhance the production of fast foods:

1. The micro credit embarked upon by the government should be extended to the fast food sellers.
2. Banks should also be encouraged to give out loans to finance the business.
3. Government should subsidize the cost of raw materials
4. Fast food producers should improve the nutritional content and safety of products so as to encourage people to buy and patronize them.

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5. Government, institutions, trained and skilled individuals should set up skill acquisition centres to help in training fast food sellers so as to make them more competent and skilled.

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